

OPEN

Practices and Challenges of Gender –Responsive Pedagogy in Government Secondary Schools of South West Shoa Zone

Teferra Berecha Yadessa¹

The purpose of this study was to examine the practices and challenges of gender-responsive pedagogy (GRP) in government secondary schools of South West Shoa Zone, Oromia regional state, Ethiopia. Three research questions were posed for determining the status of GRP, identifying hindering factors, and checking if mean differences exist among the schools towards the practices of GRP. A cross-sectional descriptive survey design was employed. One hundred sixty-four students and sixty-seven teachers were sampled using a random sampling method. Questionnaires, FGD, and document analysis were the data collecting tools. SPSS version 24 was used for analyzing the quantitative data. Mean, std. deviation, one-sample t-test, ANOVA, and multiple regression statistical tools were used for analyzing the quantitative data as the qualitative data were analyzed thematically. To this end, three main findings were reported: 1, GRP did not practice in gender-responsive ways. 2, Factors of GRP that accounted for 76 % of the variance in the practices, examined through multiple regression. Among which only the gender-biased stereotype and teachers' poor awareness have significantly explained the poor practices of GRP, $\beta \geq .437$. 3). The absence of statistical difference among the schools towards the practices of GRP was also part of the report. The qualitative data results supported that teachers discharged classroom professional responsibility in gender-insensitive ways. It validated that teachers use gendered language in classrooms, have low expectations for girl students, and were not aware of the troubles called by learners' sexual maturity and sexual harassment-related issues. Likewise, the classroom setup, classroom interactions, lesson plan preparation demonstrated teachers' negligence toward gender and the practices remained below the continuum of GRP. Finally, the researcher recommended awareness-raising training for both school communities and teachers, in particular on gender-related issues..

Keywords: Pedagogy, Gender-responsive pedagogy, Gender parity, Gender-sensitive, Gender-responsive

Introduction

" Education helps promote equality and save people from poverty. It teaches children how to be good citizens. Education is not just for the few privileged people, but for everyone. It's a basic human right " (Ban Kimoon, <https://writeanswers.royalroads.ca/faq>). In addition, UNDP (2018) calls for "no one left behind" to ensure the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development.

As part of the agenda, the international community committed to achieving the fourth Sustainable Development Goal (SDG 4): 'Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all. The SDG target 4.5 pledges, moreover, to eliminate gender disparities in education. And SDG 5 commits to achieving gender

¹Wolkite University College of Education and Behavioral Studies Department of Curriculum and Instructional Supervision Ethiopia Email: teferraberecha77@gmail.com

Copyright: © 2022 by the authors. Licensee KMF Publishers (www.kmf-publishers.com). This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

equality and empowering all women and girls (UNDP, 2018; UNESCO, 2020). These goals and targets express an aspiration towards equality, equity, and inclusion. Equality is a state of affairs (what): a result that can be observed in inputs, outputs, or outcomes. Equity is a process (how): actions aimed at ensuring equality (UNESCO, 2020) A rights-based approach involves gender equality in education related to access to and participation in education, rights within education (gender-friendly environment, processes, and outcomes), and rights through education (ie, in quality education and society). Consider the connection with broader gender equality (Gallagher, 2002).

Despite the significant advances in access to education, a huge number of girls still face the worst forms of acute exclusion out of schools (UNESCO, 2020). On the other hand, those children who have attended schools, experience prejudice, and abuse because they are boys or girls (Naomi, 2014). This is possible because teachers and students unknowingly or consciously diffuse gendered messages into the classroom as they interact through an explicit or hidden curriculum. Enduring negative gender norms in society influence teachers' attitudes, subject, and career choices, and affect women's opportunities later in life (UNESCO, 2020).

Alan et al., (2018) gender-stereotyped beliefs, rigid characterizations of gender roles, are persistent: in family, schools, professional and social life. Gender-biased stereotypes would be a challenging factor for effective classroom pedagogical practices in a multiple-way (GEM, 2016 Susuwele-Banda, 2005). For instance, there is a myth that boys are good at mathematics and science while girls are good at languages. Jobs like sweeping and cleaning are assigned to girls while boys are asked to carry things. The words used in any language are predominantly masculine. E.g. mankind, brotherhood, etc. Boys are assumed to be assertive, and confident whereas girls are supposed to respond to what has been said and

ask with a need for approval etc.. These all raised for the purpose of exemplify the existing gender biased stereotypes the would negatively impacting classroom academic performances.

Further more, majority number of teachers are not alert of the gender-specific needs of both girls and boys. Again, school management may not sufficiently address gender constraints (FAWF, 2005) that emerged as a result of sexual maturity and sexual harassment. Sanitary facilities: School buildings may not have sufficient sanitary facilities and sanitary facilities. This is a major obstacle for girls during menstruation. In co-educated schools, girls would be ashamed of the lack of shared toilet facilities and privacy.

Therefore, a comprehensive analysis of equality in educational practice through a gender perspective needs to be more than sufficient to identify gender equality (ie, equal participation or equal participation at different educational levels and streams. Achievement rate). We also need to review potential causes of fraud in classroom teaching practices, like teaching materials, water, and sanitation (UNESCO, 2020).

Gender Responsive Pedagogy (GRP) should be strengthened in such a classroom environment. To do this, you first need to look at the academic context: the lesson plan, the content, the symbols and illustrations of the student's textbook, the teaching method used, the type of assessment, etc . through the gender lens. Second, social context: language use, classroom interaction, sexual maturity issues, gender harassment, etc . should be scanned at a level where gender friendship is involved. Third, physical conditions in schools and classrooms: separate toilets for boys and girls, availability of gender-friendly seating in classrooms and laboratories, gender-friendly school buildings, etc. are all suitable for both. Boy and girls should be in the right place. Otherwise, school educational practices will be labeled as gender-free or gender-insensitive,

The large body of evidence focuses on examining different aspects of girls' schooling in terms of access, quality, empowerment, and so forth (Adhikari, 2021; Alan et al., 2018; Da Silva Borges & Labidi, 2021; Henderson, 2020; ICRW & UN Women, 2016; Johannes & Noula, 2011; Muasya & Kazungu, 2018; Zegeye, 2019). However, in Ethiopian contexts, few studies were undertaken on the topic of GRP which came up with different findings (Abraha et al., 2019). In South West, Shoa zone secondary schools' pedagogical practices have not been known. The research findings that came across in the North Wollo zone of Ethiopia, did not identify the reality of government secondary schools of Southwest Shoa. This is because gender is contexts specific which would be different based on social, geographical, cultural, and economic environments. Hence, the main purpose of this study was to investigate classroom pedagogical practices in the light of GRP and identify the hindering factors of the practices.

Problem Statements

The Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia (FDRE) adopted and incorporated the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (Assembly, 2007) (UDHR, 1948) into national policies documents and regulatory frameworks. For the manifestation of this purpose, the 1995 FDRE Constitution, the Revised Family Law (FDRE, 2000) are some to be mentioned. To enhance gender equality in education, the Ethiopian Training and Education Policy (TGE, 1994), and the recently introduced 2018/2030 education road map acknowledged the importance of closing the gap of gender disparity in terms of access and engagement in education.

Despite the significant improvement in gender parity, the problem of gender disparity between females and male persists. Further, the disparity was also observed in terms of academic achievement and learners retention rates (Wami, 2019). For instance, in the 2020/21 academic year in Mathematics and Natural

Sciences subjects 50 % of grade 11 and students who scored below 50 were girls. Similarly, among grade 12 students who scored below the cut point for university entrance score were also females in the same academic year.

Regarding Southwest Shoa Secondary schools learners completion rate, girls are still found a high rate of school leaver due to not known reasons. For example, in the 2020/21 academic year among secondary schools students who dropped schooling 74% were female students. In South West Shoa women/girls' roles and expectations are less than that of the counterpart men/boys. For instance, male students are believed good at Mathematics and Natural sciences whereas girls are good at language and social science. Belief would be extended to a classroom environment through hidden curriculum and negatively impact girl students' academic achievements. Boys get more attention in the classroom and encouragement to follow their career of choice, while girls are steered towards nurturing jobs (Korenus, 2018). Hence, the researcher felt reasonable to be voices for the voiceless as well as reversing problems that would be impeding the journey started toward ensuring the "no one will leave behind" goals (SGD 4), meeting other regional and national vision would be obstacles or educational wastage would be experienced. Hence, it would be imperative to examine classroom pedagogical practices through a gender-responsive lens. The lesson plan, classroom setup, language used, teaching-learning materials, classroom interactions, sexual maturity, and harassment handling methods ought to entertain through the gender perspective. This study has attempted to answer the following basic questions:

1. What is the status of GRP in government secondary schools of South West Shoa zone?
2. What are the major impeding factors for the effective GRP practices in government secondary schools of the South West Shoa zone?

3. Is there a significant mean difference between state secondary schools practicing GRP?

Method

Research Design

A descriptive cross-sectional design was used, including quantitative and qualitative data. In this regard, Wisdom and Cresswell, 2013) stated that using both approaches in combination had a great advantage in clarifying more information than using either one. In this study, the researcher primarily used quantitative data rather than qualitative data used to triangulate the results of quantitative data.

Data Source

Both primary and secondary sources were used to collect the required information. The main data sources were teachers, students, principals, department heads, and cluster supervisors. Teachers' made lessons and student textbooks the secondary data sources.

Sample Size and Sampling Method

According to data accessed from the Southwest Shore Zone education office, there are 11 administrative woredas/districts. Based on their geographical proximity, the researcher grouped the woredas/districts into three clusters and obtained representative samples. Accordingly, four Woredas were randomly selected from these 11 Woredas. In addition, four secondary schools were drawn using the same sampling method. Next, four principals, 16 department heads, and three cluster supervisors used the purposive sampling method. Finally, 67 teacher participants were identified using a simple random sampling technique. Again, 153 students were randomly selected.

Data Collection

To gather the required information, the researcher administered the following tools.

Questionnaire

To collect the pedagogical experience of teachers and students, the researcher asked for a close-ended questionnaire. Survey items were prepared through the five Likert point scales. The scoring scale also ranged from "strongly agree" to "strongly disagree" (strongly agree = 5, agree = 4, undecided = 3, disagree = 2, strongly disagree at all = 1) has been applied.

Document Content Analysis

To get valuable data using document analysis, a checklist that has various rubrics was equipped. Subsequently, documents like a sample of the lesson plan, students' textbooks, were critically examined against the rubrics.

Focus Group Discussion (FGD)

The FGD was further adopted because it is important to capture their views on GRP in the context of conducting separate discussions under the guidance of the researcher. To this end, he designed semi-structured questions, primarily based entirely on the main research questions.

Data Collection Procedure

Participant consent was requested before the researcher engaged in the real data collection activities. To this end, the author has submitted a letter of approval from the Zone /and Woredas/districts education offices officials Then, he briefed the goals of the examination to the respondents earlier than survey objects had been disbursed to the respondents.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher interacted with respondents in a manner respecting their cultural and private identities. The respondents confirmed their settlement and thus, participated willingly within the survey. The researcher assured the respondents their responses were used only for educational purposes.

Data Analysis

The researcher used mean and standard deviation to analyze the data collected through a close-ended questionnaire. Accordingly, expected mean scores (1) assumed as gender blind, (2) = gender insensitive, (3) = gender-neutral, (4) is used as a cut-point and assumed as gender-sensitive as (5) assumed absolute gender-responsive. The mean score below 3 indicates the low practice of GRP which would be entitled as gender irresponsive pedagogical practices, whereas the mean value (3) is assumed as gender-neutral which indicates low performance that never deviated to either gender category. Multiple regression analyses were performed for examining the major challenge that accounted for poor practices of GRP. One-way ANOVA was also employed to examine if there were significant mean differences observed in the practice of GRP among the secondary schools. The qualitative data, which was collected through document analysis, and FGD, were analyzed thematically.

Results

The first objective of this study was to investigate the current practical status of GRP in government secondary schools of the South West Shoa zone, Oromia regional state of Ethiopia. To meet this purpose, relevant quantitative and qualitative data were collected from pertinent participants through various tools. The data was generated through close-

ended questionnaires imported to the SPSS computer software version 24 and analyzed through mean, std. deviation and one sample t-test whereas the qualitative data were analyzed thematically as follows.

Current status of GRP

For research question 1, a one-sample t-test analysis was performed to determine the overall status of the GRP sample mean value compared with the predefined hypothesized population mean value which is (4.0). Further, the specific dimensions of GRP were analyzed using mean and std. deviation. To do this, first of all, to be certain if the assumptions for the one-sample t-test work. Accordingly, it was checked that data used were normally distributed, as examined through Shapiro-Wilk's test ($P > .05$) and there were no outliers in the data, as checked by inspection of a box plot. Eventually, the following data analysis results were drawn.

To have specific insight into the practices of GRP each dimension data result is presented (see table 3) below. Accordingly, the classroom setup dimension of GRP was found ($M=3.2, SD=.99$) as sexual harassment became ($M=2.5, SD=.79$). Next, the lesson, teaching-learning material, and classroom dynamics aspects were found ($M=3.0, SD=1.01$), ($M=3.1, SD=.85$) and ($M=3.1, SD=.94$) respectively. And the language usage ($M=2.6, SD=1.0$) and handling of sexual maturation data result became ($M=2.8, SD=.83$)

Table 3:
One-Sample Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Language of GRP	220	2.6	1.0
Class set up for GRP	220	3.2	.99
Lesson plan preparation	67	3.0	1.01
Material used	231	3.1	.85
Class dynamics	231	3.1	.94
Handling sexual maturation	231	2.8	.83
addressing sexual harassment	231	2.5	.79

Further, the above dimensions of data were computed into a single overall GRP variable. To that one-sample statistics (see table 4) data analysis was performed to compare the samples' mean values with the

hypothesized mean value. Accordingly, the overall GRP descriptive statistics data analysis result became (M = 2.9, SD = .63), whereas the one-sample t-test (see table 4) was $t(230) = -22.9, p < 0.05$ (two-tailed).

Table 4
One-Sample Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Overall GRP	220	2.9	.63	.04147

Note. Total possible scores range from 1 to 5

Table 5
One-Sample Test

Test Value = 4						
	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Overall GRP	-22.860	230	.000	-.94805	-1.0298	-.8663

Further, FGD was performed with the view to triangulate the quantitative data results. The contents of the discussions, their meanings, and particular implications were determined in terms of the research question posed. understanding how the participants think about the level to which classroom pedagogical experiences are gender-responsive in science and

mathematics subjects. Accordingly, the central idea of the participants' discussion assured that gender issues through pedagogical points of view did not gain due attention to the continuum it would be. The principals, department heads, and cluster supervisors who participated commonly admitted that even if they have awareness issues associated with a gender, they had

hesitation regarding its effective practices. They commonly agree upon the existence of insufficient attention on gender at the time of planning and implementation of classroom instructions. However, they knew that gender has been the cutting issue for the Ethiopian government for the past few years with the view to ensure the national-wide motto ‘Education for all. The participants also raised some promising practices accomplished for promoting gender equality in their school contexts. For instance, they mentioned an establishment of schools level girls’ clubs, building separate latrines for both females and males as good practices for responding to gender-based needs. Some participants further added that even if it’s not adequate there was a time when NGOs distributed some sanitary materials for female students.

However, they did not hide that some teachers use abusive language that degrades and underestimate female students’ roles to be played in academic activities. Again, they openly admitted that the issues of handling sexual maturation and harassment persisting as a poorly addressed area of concern. Generally, Classroom instructional activities had not been carried out in an approach gender-sensitive way across the participants’ respective schools.

Some of the participants forwarded their idea as follows:

P10

There were government documents for enforcing the equal engagements of boy and girl students. This would be manifested in our practices of structuring school-based committees.

P1 2

In our school context, we built toilets separately with the view to favor gender privacy. This all promotes Adjusted R =.796. Significant variables are shown below:

Predictor Variables	Beta	P
Gender biased stereotypes	-.947	P=.000
Teachers’ poor awareness	-.437	P=.001

gender equality even if I do not mean it is adequate. But, in terms of classroom-related instructional practices, it is more teachers oriented.

P8

“ To speak frankly while I’m preparing a lesson plan, I always focus on other aspects of instructional issues. not a gender issue. I believe all the rest teachers did the same in our school”

P14

“ I have not reflected on my classroom experiences in terms of GRP, which I believe something should be. We have not forced teachers of our school in line with this”

Finally, document analysis was carried out for supporting the quantitative data result using scrutinizing teachers’ lesson plans and students’ textbooks. Teachers made lesson plans were evaluated to judge the extent to which the documents were planned in ways that considered the learning needs of both girls and boys. Unfortunately, all the lesson plans that the researcher examined failed to incorporate gender-oriented terms in the documents, tone into them.

In general, the results of the close-ended survey items, the FGD, and the document content analysis were supporting the same data results on the practices of GRP

Factors affecting GRP

The second research question of this study was concerned with identifying the major challenging factors for effective practices of GRP in the research context. To meet this purpose a multiple regression analysis was performed on to the potential factors that had a significant correlation with variable GRP. Accordingly, by using the enter method, a significant model emerged ($F(4, 230)=225.885, P < 0.05$ resulted.

Hence, the gender-biased stereotype, and teachers' poor awareness toward GRP were found to be significant independent variables.

Note: Economic-related factors and school management-related factors were statistically insignificant in this model while school facilities-related factors were excluded from the model due to the collinearity problem.

Difference among schools

One-way ANOVA was performed to determine if significant GRP performance differences exist among the government secondary schools of the southwest Shoa zone. Likewise, there was a statistically significant difference among the schools as determined by one-way ANOVA ($F(3, 230) = 5.39, P = .001$).

Table 6
Analysis of ANOVA on GRP

	Sum Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	13.111	3	4.370	5.385	.001
Within Groups	184.223	227	.812		
Total	197.333	230			

Discussion

This study investigated the Southwest Shoa Zone, government secondary schools practices of GRP. It specifically examined dimensions of GRP: the lesson plan, classroom set up, classroom dynamics, language usage, teaching-learning materials, sexual maturity, and sexual harassment. Identifying potential hindering factors of effective GRP and identifying if significant differences exist among the participant schools were also another concern of this study. To meet the purposes both quantitative and qualitative data were generated from related participants. The numerical data were imported to SPSS computer software and mean, standard deviation, one-sample t-test, and multiple regression were calculated. Further, the qualitative that used to support the quantitative data results were analyzed thematically in line with the posed research questions.

The current performance status of GRP

The first result of the data analysis goes to determine the status of GRP in Southwest Shoa zone secondary schools. Consequently, the finding confirmed that the practices of GRP were not being implemented in a

gender-responsive approach. The finding indicated the practices of GRP in the secondary schools were being practiced in the continuum closest to be gender-neutral pedagogical practices. That means the overall practices of GRP in the secondary schools of the Southwest Shoa zone were below the hypothesized value. Classroom teaching-learning processes in Mathematics and natural science subjects were not being practiced in a way that equally addressed the learning needs of both boy and girl students. In other words, gender issues did not gain adequate attention in the Mathematics and Natural Science classrooms instructional activities of southwest Shoa secondary schools. The finding also assured that the gender disparity observed in academic achievement and low retention rate of male and female students was due to one factor of gender irresponsive pedagogical practices in the schools. More specifically, the GRP dimensions:- language usage, handling sexual maturation and harassment were quite practiced in gender in-sensitive ways. The dimensions of teaching-learning material, classroom setup, classroom dynamics, and lesson plan are relatively undertaken in gender-neutral methods. But, the language usage,

sexual maturity, and sexual harassment aspects performed even below the continuum were supposed to be gender-neutral.

This finding was not a surprise because the schools are located in male-dominated social contexts. Due to the bilateral influences that exist between schools and society.

Major challenges of GRP

The second finding of the study pointed out the major impeding factors of effective practices of GRP in the Southwest Shoa zone government Secondary schools. Consequently, gender-biased stereotypes and teachers' poor awareness of GRP were found to be major hindering factors for effective practices of GRP in government secondary schools of the Southwest Shoa zone. This finding was what was expected because a gender-biased stereotype is a long-dated social in local societies. These biased beliefs and attitudes have been extended to the classroom environments through the hidden curriculum. The local communities believe males are better in Mathematics and Science school subjects than females whereas female students are better in language and other social science subjects. The researcher himself has lived experiences regarding the expectation and positions females own in society. These beliefs are inevitably influencing classroom instruction unless special attention is provided. However, there was an improvement regarding girls' societal positions compared to the past.

On the other hand, teachers' poor awareness or poor commitment was found to be the other hindering factor of the effective practices of GRP in the Southwest Shoa government secondary schools. The lesson plan teachers prepare, the instructional methodology that they implement, classroom set up, classroom interaction, handling sexual maturation, and sexual harassment all need well awareness and commitment. These all dimensions of GRP require

planning and implementing in a way equally accommodating boys' and girls' learning needs. This finding is also expected because teachers were never given adequate awareness to GRP both pre-service or in-service training. Merely hearing gender issues through mass media and other means never makes teachers gender-sensitive professional practitioners.

Difference among Schools

Finally, the third result of this study revealed the absence of statistically significant difference among the government secondary schools of the Southwest Shoa zone with a link to the effective practice of GRP. This means, the government secondary schools of southwest Shoa zone implementing GRP to the continuum below to the expected continuum of gender-responsive. Classroom pedagogical practices were never being undertaken in gender-sensitive ways rather carried out in methods insufficiently addressing gender learning needs in academic, social, and physical classroom environments. This finding is also what was expected as the schools were located in similar socio-economic contexts.

The findings

These all findings have practical importance for all government secondary schools generally communities particularly for natural Science and Mathematics teachers, as it would be an alarm bell for reconsidering the practices being engaged in the relation to ensuring the 2030 SD agenda. It would urge stakeholders to provide essential attention not only for education access but also for classroom pedagogical practices for effecting gender equality at schools. This is true as the research findings affirmed the status and impeding factors of gender friend instructional practices across the schools. The findings were helpful as they uncover the classrooms' factors that directly correlate with learners' academic success and promote students' retention rate in schools.

The findings from this study seem consistent with (Abraha et al., 2021, Dorji, 2020, Fentie, (2017), Muasya & Kazungu, 2018, Kahamba et al., 2017, Tilahun, 2021). Overall, findings revealed the degree to which classroom pedagogical practices accomplished in line with gender-sensitive that were found to be below the continuum. However, a finding was inconsistent with a study done by (Abraha et al., 2019) about GRP in secondary schools of West north Wollo Zone, Ethiopia which found practices of GRP as effective concerning language usage, classroom setups, classroom interaction, and addressing sexual harassment.

Conclusion

Education has been admitted as the only effective tool for ensuring issues like gender equality, social and economic development, etc. This would happen only if people equally accessed and benefited from it regardless of any sort of differences. Accessing schooling opportunities alone would not fulfill the need for education unless it equally benefits both female and male learners. Classroom pedagogical practices that operate within varied social, physical, and academic contexts would either properly shape or further reinforce social evils unless a close look is given. A hidden curriculum is a channel through which these views and practices are communicated among school communities. In this regard, the current study found that the gender-biased social stereotype and teachers' poor awareness toward GRP were significantly negatively impacted the classroom in SouthWest Shoa government secondary schools. Further, this study determined the degree to which the classroom pedagogical practices were gender friends in the research setting. It's known that pedagogical practices are not being accomplished in line with the assumption of gender-responsive.

Recommendation

Based on the results obtained, the following recommendations were drawn.

- Teachers should be accustomed to periodically reflecting on their classroom pedagogical experiences through gender-responsive perspectives
- Teachers should be given awareness-raising training on GRP both during pre-services and in-services
- Schools need to urge teachers to be involved in a continuous professional development program that embodied the issues of GRP
- The zonal, woredas education offices and schools :

Students to classroom ratio need to be to the standard to facilitate quality instruction

engage more female teachers to models, and sense a more safe educational environment for girls

References

- Abraha, M., Dagne, A., & Seifu, A. (2019). Gender Responsive Pedagogy: Practices, Challenges & Opportunities - A Case of Secondary Schools of North Wollo Zone, Ethiopia. *Journal of Education, Society and Behavioural Science*. <https://doi.org/10.9734/jesbs/2019/v30i330128>
- Adhikari, H. K. (2021). Teachers' Mindset on Gender Responsive Pedagogy (GRP) in Mathematics Classroom. *Curriculum Development Journal*, 29(43). <https://doi.org/10.3126/cdj.v29i43.41068>
- Alan, S., Ertac, S., & Mumcu, I. (2018). Gender stereotypes in the classroom and effects on achievement. *Review of Economics and Statistics*, 100(5), 876–890. https://doi.org/10.1162/rest_a_00756
- Assembly, T. G. (2007). Universal Declaration of Human Rights (Chaukese). *Asia-Pacific Journal on Human Rights and the Law*, 8(1), 101–106. <https://doi.org/10.1163/157181507782200222>

- Da Silva Borges, A. L. L., & Labidi, S. (2021). Rethinking What It Is to Be a Feminist. *Advances in Applied Sociology*, 11(04), 206–212.
<https://doi.org/10.4236/aasoci.2021.114017>
- Dorji, T. (2020). Gender Responsive Pedagogy Awareness and Practices: A Case Study of a Higher Secondary School under Thimphu Thromde, Bhutan. *International Journal of Linguistics and Translation Studies*, 1(2).
- Gallagher, J. J. (2002). Gifted Education in the 21st Century. In *Gifted Education International* (Vol. 16, Issue 2).
<https://doi.org/10.1177/026142940201600203>
- Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia (FDRE).1995. The Constitution of the Federal Republic of Ethiopia. Addis Ababa.
- _____.2000. Revised Family Law. Proclamation No. 213/2000. Addis Ababa
- Forum for African Women Educationalists (FAWE)(2005). Gender Responsive Pedagogy: A Teacher’s Handbook. Nairobi 00505, Kenya
- GEM, U. (2016). “ Addressing gender stereotypes in the classroom: how to achieve a conducive environment for adolescent girls ’ learning ?”
- Henderson, C. (2020). *Gender-responsive education in the context of COVID-19. December.*
<https://doi.org/10.34218/IJM.12.1.2021.138>
<https://writeanswers.royalroads.ca/faq>
- ICRW, & UN Women. (2016). *Gender Responsive Governance. November.*
- Johannes, T. A., & Noula, A. G. (2011). Gender and increased access to schooling in Cameroon: A marginal benefit incidence analysis. *Journal of International Women’s Studies*, 12(1), 94–106.
- Kahamba, J. S., Massawe, F. A., & Kira, E. S. (2017). IMP Awareness and Practice of Gender Responsive Pedagogy in Higher Learning Institutions: The Case of Sokoine University of Agriculture, Tanzania. *Journal of Education, Humanities & Sciences*, 6(2).
- Korenius, S. (2018). *Gender-sensitive education. 2011.*
- Muasya, J., & Kazungu, T. (2018). ‘The unfinished business’: Exploring teachers’ views on gender and pedagogical practices in public preschools in Nairobi county, Kenya. *African Educational Research Journal*, 6(1), 10–19.
<https://doi.org/10.30918/aerj.61.18.007>
- Naomi Netsayi Wekwete,(2014). Gender and Economic Empowerment in Africa: Evidence and Policy, *Journal of African Economies*,23(1) 87–127, <https://doi.org/10.1093/jae/ejt022>
- Susuwele-Banda, W. J. (2005). Classroom assessment in Malawi: Teachers’ perceptions and practices in mathematics. *Curriculum and Instruction, Ph.D.*, 184.
- UNDP. (2018). What does it Mean to Leave No One Behind? *United Nations Development Programme, July*, 1–28.
- UNESCO. (2020). *Global education monitoring report 2020: Gender report, A new generation: 25 years of efforts for gender equality in education.* <https://en.unesco.org/gem-report/2020genderreport>
- Wami, G. (2019). *Major Problems Affecting the Academic.*
- Wisdom, J., & Creswell, J. W. (2013). Mixed Methods: Integrating Quantitative and Qualitative Data Collection and Analysis While Studying Patient-Centered Medical Home Models (pp. 1-5). PCMH Research Methods Series 13.
- Zegeye, A. T. (2019). Article Review on the Current Education policy and curriculum issues in Ethiopia: Trends that Reveal the Problem of Practicing Policy Provisions in Institutions. *Open Journal of Language and Linguistics*, 2, 8.